

NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS)

A 5-year mission to accelerate adoption of open science

Goals:

- Increase understanding and adoption of open science principles and techniques
- Broaden participation by historically excluded communities
- Accelerate scientific discovery

Open Science 101

A community-developed introduction to **core open science skills**

Open Science 101: Benefits of open science presented as a scientific workflow

**Ethos
of Open
Science**

**Open
Science
Tools**

**Open-
source
Code**

**Open
Data**

**Open
Results**

Images: JSC, JPL, & MSFC

